

Review article

Electrodeposition of nano- and micro-materials: Advancements in electrocatalysts for electrochemical applications

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ABSTRACT

Electrodeposition is an essential technique for the fabrication of nanomaterials and thin films based on passing an electric current through a support electrode in contact with a solution containing a metal salt dissolved in it. Commonly referred to as 'electroplating' in industrial settings, this method is extensively used for developing a wide range of electrocatalytic materials due to its simplicity, versatility, cost-effectiveness, and efficiency. Despite its widespread use and growing popularity for electrocatalyst fabrication, electrodeposition processes are often misunderstood, and many research studies have not fully leveraged their potential due to a lack of understanding and optimisation of key aspects of the process; consequently, researchers may miss straightforward opportunities to maximise the performance and functionality of electrodeposited electrocatalysts, as small variations in the electrodeposition process parameters can have significant effects on their activity, selectivity and lifespan. To address these issues, the present review delves deeper into the fundamental principles of electrodeposition, explores the mechanisms of electrodeposited material growth and discusses potentiostatic, galvanostatic and pulse electrodeposition techniques in achieving uniform and high-quality films. Moreover, the review discusses how different operation parameters such as *pH*, temperature or current density influence the process itself and the properties of deposited materials and films. The use of electrodeposited materials as catalysts in various electrochemical applications such as CO₂ reduction, water splitting, pollutant removal and energy storage, among others, is also reviewed, along with a stimulating discussion on challenges faced by the research community and future opportunities for electrodeposition techniques in the area of electrocatalysis. By providing a comprehensive understanding of how process parameters affect the activity, selectivity, stability, and durability of electrodeposited electrocatalysts, this review underscores the importance of electrodeposition in advancing sustainable and efficient energy solutions.

1. Introduction

Electrodeposition refers to the electrochemical process of depositing solid materials on a substrate electrode. Traditionally, it has been primarily associated with the deposition of metals from an aqueous electrolyte onto the cathode in an electrochemical cell. However, in modern applications, a diverse range of materials, including pure metals, alloys, semiconductors and polymers, can be electrodeposited onto either the cathode or anode. These materials can form different structures, ranging from macro-scale structures such as coatings and thin films to nano-scale constructions such as nanotubes, nanorods, nanowires and nanoclusters [1]. This broad range of architectures is facilitated by employing various

media, including aqueous solutions, non-aqueous solvents, ionic melts, and ionic liquids [2–4].

The origins of electroplating can be traced back to Volta's groundbreaking discovery of 'chemical electricity' production in 1799 [5]. This discovery sparked widespread interest in electrically induced chemical reactions, leading to the electrolysis of various solutions and the formation of metallic deposits. Initially, these early deposits were often irregular in shape and did not immediately indicate the future potential of the electroplating industry. For example, in 1837, G. Bird documented his experiments, observing the formation of "a crust of metallic nickel on the negative electrode, often with a silvery lustre on the surface in contact with platinum," when using NiCl₂ and NiSO₄ solutions [6]. At that time,

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the primary practical application of electrodeposition was electroforming, which focused mainly on depositing copper from simple copper salt solutions [5]. However, research and development in the electrodeposition of metals blossomed over the century and a half to come, leading to the fabrication of a broad range of materials, thin films, and coatings. These advancements significantly contributed to the emergence of diverse applications across multiple industries (e.g. surface finishing, decorative/protecting coatings, electronics, functional materials) [7–12].

Despite the widespread use of electroplating in industry, the electrodeposition of catalysts for electrochemical applications did not receive much attention from the research community until relatively recently, when electrodeposition techniques have become a promising approach to tune both the structure and characteristics of electrocatalysts [13]. This has led to the appearance of several electrodeposition-based review articles for electrocatalysts in recent years. Some of these are more focused on specific electrochemical applications (e.g. (hydro)oxides for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) [14], transition metal-based catalysts for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) [15]); some are focused on surface nanostructuring or atomic-level catalysts [13,16]; whereas a few others cover energy applications more generally [17,18]. However, whereas these reviews focus on the wide range of electrocatalysis applications that can significantly benefit from electrodeposited materials, the wide range of operational parameters that influence these processes is generally overlooked. In the present review, we do not only review the basic principles of electrodeposition processes and explore the various electrochemical applications where electrodeposited catalysts are playing a crucial role, but we also discuss in detail the role that key process parameters such as electrolyte, *pH*, temperature or current density have on the characteristics and electrochemical performance of the resulting electrocatalysts.

2. Fundamentals of electrodeposition

2.1. Electrodeposition process

Fig. 1 displays the typical setup for the electrodeposition of metals over a conductive substrate. The cell consists of a minimum of two metal electrodes submerged in a liquid medium: the cathode (or working electrode, WE), which is where the metal would deposit, and the anode (or counter electrode, CE), which may either be a piece of the same metal being electrodeposited (which will oxidise as the process proceeds, replenishing the metal cations in the solution as they are consumed at the cathode) or an inert material. Both electrodes, which are immersed in the electrolyte containing the metal cations taking part in the process, are connected to a power source that drives a potential gradient between the electrodes, setting the potential of the cathode (or the anode) below (or above) the equilibrium potential of the reaction of interest occurring at the surface of the electrode. This electric potential also drives the transport of charge within the system, with metal cations travelling towards the cathode (where they will electrochemically reduce and form the deposit that gives the process its name) and salt anions moving towards the anode. In addition, a reference electrode (RE) may be used to provide a stable and precise potential reference in relation to the cathode, allowing for better control and monitoring of its potential when using a potentiostat as the power source.

The setup shown in Fig. 1 describes an electrochemical setup where the reaction of interest is a process of cathodic nature (i.e. reduction reaction at the surface of the cathode), which is the case in the vast majority of electrodeposition processes (e.g. electrodeposition of metals). However, it is worth noting at this point that anodic electrodeposition processes do exist (e.g. electrodeposition of metal oxides), although their industrial importance is significantly smaller than that of cathodic electrodeposition processes. In those cases, the WE would be the anode, the RE would be used to control and monitor the potential of the anode and the CE would be the cathode.

Fig. 1. Electrochemical cell used for an electrodeposition process where the deposition takes place at the cathode.

Whether it is a cathodic or anodic process, as any other electrochemical process, the electrodeposition of materials follows Faraday's Laws of Electrolysis, which state that the amount of 'chemical change' (i.e. products being produced or reactants being consumed) generated by passing a current through the interface between an electrode and an electrolyte is proportional to both the charge involved and the equivalent weight of the specific chemical substance experiencing said 'chemical change' [20,21]. If only the reaction of interest occurs at the electrode and a constant current is applied during the whole process, these Laws can be defined as:

$$m_i = \frac{M_i I t}{n_i F} \quad (1)$$

where m is the mass of either the reactants consumed or products produced at the electrode, M and α_i are, respectively, their molar mass and stoichiometric coefficient in the reaction at the electrode, n is the number of electrons involved in the reaction, t is the time over which the electric current I is applied and F is Faraday's constant. Therefore, Faraday's Laws of Electrolysis can be used to estimate the rate of the process and the amount of material deposited. Besides Faraday's Laws of Electrolysis, there are other fundamental electrochemical concepts intrinsically relevant to electrodeposition that are worth knowing to fully understand how electrodeposition processes work. These concepts cover a wide range of factors, such as thermodynamics (i.e. equilibrium potential, Nernst equation), kinetics (i.e. Butler-Volmer equation, overpotential), resistance to charge transport (i.e. ohmic losses), setup design (e.g. primary, secondary and tertiary current distribution) and, when relevant, mass transport limitations (i.e. limiting current, concentration overpotential). Covering all of these concepts in detail would require a remarkably large amount of space, which is why the reader is encouraged to explore comprehensive readings on these topics available in the literature [22–24].

Electrodeposition processes are highly valued in research and industrial applications for their ability to synthesise a wide range of materials (i.e. nano- and micron-scale structures, thin films and coatings) on all sorts of conductive surfaces, including complex and irregular surfaces [25–28]. In many instances, the composition of electrodeposited materials can be precisely controlled by adjusting the concentration of the substance being deposited in the electrolyte [29–31], allowing for tailored properties of the final product.

Fig. 2. System model illustrating metal distribution relationships. Based on Rudzki [19].

Electroplating is also recognised for its flexibility and efficiency; electrodeposition processes can be operated across a wide temperature range, typically between 15 and 70 °C, depending on specific deposition needs of both process and material being deposited [24]. Compared to other methods, electrodeposition is notably energy-efficient and simple to operate; high deposition rates can be achieved by such processes, making electrodeposition an ideal option for large-scale manufacturing and rapid production cycles [32]. However, it is important to understand that electrodeposition processes involve many variables that influence the overall procedure and must be controlled. Rudzki's system model [19], presented in Fig. 2, illustrates the range and complex interdependence of electroplating operation parameters, highlighting the interrelation between different variables of the process. This model provides a detailed overview of how parameters such as electrolyte composition, temperature, pH, current density, and additives interact and influence any electrodeposition process. Mapping these interactions illustrates how changes in one parameter can impact many others, affecting the properties and quality of the final electrodeposited material.

2.2. Mechanisms

If one considers the wide industrial implementation and application of electrodeposition processes, they may be misled to think that such processes are simple and straightforward. This could not be further from the truth: electrodeposition processes involve multiple stages and complex mechanisms.

A good example of this is shown in Fig. 3 for the electrodeposition of materials from an aqueous electrolyte [33]. Initially, ions in the aqueous electrolyte interact with water molecules through ion-dipole forces or complex molecules (e.g. additives) via covalent interactions. When a potential difference is then applied between the electrodes, these solvated ions will travel from the bulk of the aqueous electrolyte towards the surface of the electrode by diffusion, convection or migration until they reach the boundary of the double layer. At this point, the primary stage of the deposition process begins as the ions cross the electric field interface. Upon reaching the outer Helmholtz plane (OHP) of the double layer, these ions will undergo a charge-transfer reaction, completely or partially shedding their solvating water sheath before adsorbing onto the electrode surface as ad-ions or ad-atoms.

Fig. 3. Schematic picture of the nucleation and growth during a typical electrodeposition process from an electrolyte consisting of (1) ion transport from bulk electrolyte to the OHP; (2) transfer of ions across the electrical double layer; (3) de-solvation (or dehydration) in part or in total, and formation of ad-ions and ad-atoms, respectively; (4) surface diffusion of ad-atoms; (5) nucleation of stable atomic clusters; (6) irreversible incorporation of ad-atoms in the atomic lattice and establishment of a peculiar crystallographic texture and morphology or electrocrystallisation. F. Nasirpour, *Fundamentals and Principles of Electro-Position, Electrodeposition of Nanostructured Materials*, pp 75-121, 2017, Springer. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-44920-3_3. Reprinted with permission from Springer Nature.

The formation of ad-ions and ad-atoms on the surface of the substrate and the subsequent nucleation and growth of the film then follow a complex pathway influenced by the surface energy and morphology of the substrate. In this regard, film growth ideally occurs on atomically flat substrates, but real surfaces have defects described by the terrace-ledge-kink (TLK) model (Fig. 4) [34]. Various growth sites, such as flat surfaces, kinks and edges, play an essential role in this process. Initially, an ion partially contacts the substrate at a specific site, becoming a surface ad-ion. This ad-ion retains some charge and some hydration water molecules associated with it. As the ad-ion migrates to different growth sites, the number of surrounding water molecules decreases, progressively from flat surfaces to steps, kinks, and vacancies. This stage, known as surface diffusion, involves a random-walk diffusion process where ad-atoms move on the substrate surface. During this process, ad-atoms eventually replace all hydration water molecules with coordinating metal atoms, resulting in a “zero charge” ad-atom that can be incorporated into the lattice. The surface diffusion facilitates the movement of ad-atoms from flat sites to step sites and then to kink sites, eventually leading to their incorporation to the lattice. This process culminates in the nucleation of stable atomic clusters.

The complexity of electrodeposition processes is also reflected in the redox mechanisms involved. Generally, the overall redox reaction for the electrodeposition of metals from an electrolyte containing metal ions M^{n+} can be written as:

where M is the metal being reduced or deposited, and n is the number of electrons required for the metal to become neutral (0 oxidation state). However, the ‘real’ redox mechanisms can be far more complex. For example, for the electrodeposition of Ni, whereas the overall reaction would be $Ni^{2+} + 2 e^{-} \rightarrow Ni$, the mechanism generally followed is:

1. $Ni^{2+} + X^{-} \rightarrow NiX^{+}$
2. $NiX^{+} + e^{-} \rightarrow NiX_{ads}$
3. $NiX_{ads} + e^{-} \rightarrow Ni + X^{-}$

where X^{-} can be either OH^{-} , SO_4^{2-} or Cl^{-} , depending on the electrolyte [35,36]. In the case of a classic Watts bath for Ni electroplating, X^{-} would be Cl^{-} and the second reaction included above would be the rate-determining step of the overall electrochemical reduction process [35]. Redox mechanisms like the one just described may become even more

Fig. 4. Schematic diagram of the substrate surface described by the terrace-step-kink model. Reprinted from *Computational Materials Science*, Vol 48, Jian-Hua Zhang et al., Comparative study of Cu_{13} and Co_{13} clusters deposition and diffusion on the $Cu(001)$ surface, pages 250-257, © 2010, with permission from Elsevier.

complex depending on the specific operation of the electrodeposition process, as a wide range of parameters and variables like those included in Fig. 2 will influence the reaction pathways [37].

2.3. Methods

In broad terms, any electrodeposition process can be roughly controlled by either regulating the potential of the electrode where the electrodeposition is taking place (which is practically done by applying an electric potential/voltage gradient between the electrodes) or by setting the current passed through the electrodes. This is reflected in the two primary methods used in electrodeposition, potentiostatic and galvanostatic, with each one offering unique advantages suited to different applications [38]. In potentiostatic electrodeposition, the potential applied to the working electrode is maintained constant while the current fluctuates over time [24]. This method uses a potentiostat to maintain a fixed potential for the working electrode, measured relative to a reference electrode. This precise control over the electrode’s potential allows for accurate management of the deposition process, making it ideal for applications requiring detailed control over the coating’s properties. On the other hand, galvanostatic electrodeposition operates by maintaining a constant current density between the anode and the cathode of the electrochemical cell using a direct current source [39]. However, variations in potential can occur due to factors such as changes in the surface condition of the electrodes (roughness and morphology) and fluctuations in the composition of the electrolyte solution near the electrode, including variations in chemical species concentration and pH [24].

In addition to the galvanostatic and potentiostatic approaches, pulse electrodeposition combines elements of both techniques by using electrical pulses generated through signal amplitude modulation over time with specified waveforms [33]. These electrical pulses can be categorised into unipolar or single polarity pulses, where all pulses are in the same direction (on-off), and bipolar pulses, which alternate between positive and negative directions (reverse current). In bipolar pulsed current, metal deposition occurs during the cathodic pulse, while partial metal dissolution takes place during the anodic pulse period [40]. Pulsed electrodeposition is particularly advantageous for the fabrication of smoother, less porous and more uniform films with fine-grained deposits. It typically does not require additives in the electrolyte, and the electrolyte composition can use less metal salt [38].

2.4. Operating parameters

In electrodeposition processes, the resulting nano- and micro-structured materials, thin films, and coatings are controlled by a wide range of interrelated operating parameters and variables that significantly impact the quality and composition of the deposited material [41]. These parameters can be categorised into three main groups [42]:

- Electrolyte: This includes the concentration of the electrolyte, metal ions, pH, complexing agents, additives, etc.
- Operational conditions: These include current density, temperature, bath agitation, and the type of current applied (i.e., constant, pulse, reverse, etc.).
- Other parameters: These include cell geometry, cathode shape, deposit thickness, substrate material/surface, etc.

As previously mentioned, each parameter affects the composition and properties of electrodeposited coatings in various ways depending on the specific deposition system. These parameters collectively influence the characteristics of electrodeposited materials, and optimising these variables enables precise control over film morphology, adhesion, and performance, enhancing their functionality in diverse industrial and scientific contexts. In this regard, several works available in the literature have demonstrated that further enhancement of the mechanical, physical, and chemical characteristics of electrodeposited materials can be achieved through the appropriate selection of the electrodeposition process conditions. This paper reviews the effects of the most relevant parameters (i.e. those that can exert the greatest influence in the process and characteristics of the resulting materials) on the electrodeposition of electrocatalysts for electrochemical applications and explores how their overall performance is affected.

2.4.1. Electrolyte

As in any electrochemical process, selecting or developing the right electrolyte is crucial to facilitate reactant mass transport, achieve enough ionic conductivity to reduce ohmic losses and deliver the best combination of ions and molecules for the double layer forming at the surface of the electrode, which will translate in the appropriate kinetics for the process [40,43]. Electrodeposition processes are normally conducted in aqueous electrolytes, although non-aqueous electrolytes [44], particularly ionic liquids [45], have also received wide attention from the research community. More often than not, electrolytes incorporate additives that serve specific functions in electroplating [23], as they can reduce internal deposit stresses, promote anode dissolution, enhance current efficiency, inhibit dendritic growth, and prevent pitting through surface adsorption [46].

Many different studies have explored the influence of the electrolyte on the electrodeposition of a wide range of materials. For instance, research on the effect of different additives on Zn-Sn alloy electrodeposition from deep eutectic solvents showed that both boric and nicotinic acids acted as effective brightening agents in those conditions, improving surface quality and corrosion resistance [47]. Studies on nickel electrodeposition from Watts baths with surfactants such as sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) or polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) emphasised their impacts on brightness and corrosion resistance [48]. In addition, factorial design approaches have revealed the synergistic and antagonistic effects of commercial additives on electrodeposited Ni materials, leading to the optimisation of properties such as brightness and charge transfer resistance [48].

2.4.2. pH

Regulating the pH of the electrolyte is essential in electrochemistry in general and electrodeposition processes in particular, as it significantly influences the quality and characteristics of the deposited materials in the latter. Setting the appropriate pH can enhance current efficiency and prevent irregular deposition patterns due to the interaction of chemical species with the electrode potential [49]. Electrolyte pH can affect properties such as the adhesion of the deposited materials to the substrate, their uniformity, hardness or even resistance to hydrogen embrittlement; pH can also impact the relative concentrations of electroactive species in the solution/electrode interface, potentially affecting electrochemical equilibria [24]. Moreover, in the case of metal or metal oxide electroplating in aqueous electrolytes, pH directly influences the Faradaic efficiency and the precipitation and formation of hydroxides

(both inherently related to undesired HER or OER occurring at the surface of the cathode or anode, respectively), all of which may determine the bulk properties of the deposited material. For instance, when varying the pH between 6.1 and 11 in the electrodeposition of Cu₂O thin films on indium tin oxide (ITO)-coated glass substrates, significant changes in the growth, structure, and morphology of the deposits were observed [50]. Conducting the process at higher pH values led to improved crystallinity and increased crystallite size; the preferential orientation and surface morphology of the deposits also changed, transitioning from spherical shapes to pyramidal at higher pH.

The influence of electrolyte pH on the characteristics and properties of electrodeposited materials may be even more significant in the case of alloys. Fe-W-Zn alloy electroplating is a good example, as bath pH significantly affects the electrodeposited material's composition, morphology, and corrosion resistance; at pH < 8, Zn content within 1.5-2% provided the coating with a smooth, fine-granular surface exhibiting enhanced passivation and corrosion resistance. On the other hand, when the pH was increased to 9.0, the excess free NH₃ made Zn deposition more difficult, reducing the Zn content and leading to lower-quality coatings with poorer performance [51].

pH also had a significant impact on the electrodeposition of Re-Ir-Ni alloy coatings from citrate-containing electrolytes [52]. Increasing the pH from 2 to 8 at 70 °C enhanced the Faradaic efficiency of the process, resulting in greater deposition rates and a significant variation of the alloy composition. Moreover, whereas amorphous and crack-free deposits were produced at pH = 2, electrodeposition at pH ≥ 4 or higher resulted in crystalline coatings with columnar crystals and micro-cracks over their surface. All of these results clearly demonstrate the direct impact that pH has on both the process and properties of electrodeposited materials.

2.4.3. Agitation

One particular aspect of electrolytes that is sometimes overlooked is the effect of stirring them during the process. Electrolyte agitation often influences deposit quality and morphology; it can inhibit crystal growth and promote the formation of smaller crystallites, becoming a factor in controlling crystal size in some cases [53]. Agitation ensures thorough mixing of the metal salts dissolved in the solvent, enhancing mass transport of electroactive species to and from the surface of the electrode surface, thereby increasing the deposition rate [54] in those cases where the electrodeposition process is conducted under mass transport control (Fig. 6; it also helps to minimise the effect of gas bubbles that could otherwise cause pitting, improving the quality of the deposited layer. In the case of alloy electroplating, agitation can also significantly impact both the composition of the deposit and the current efficiency; however, it remains challenging to draw conclusive facts about this precise impact on material composition due to varying conditions during electrodeposition processes involving alloys [55].

However, the advantages of agitation are not universally applicable. In some instances, agitation can lead to a non-uniform distribution of the plating solution [56], and excessive stirring can lead to micro-cracks and poor adhesion due to rapid solution diffusion affecting crystal growth rates [57]. Therefore, a thorough consideration of benefits and potential issues is necessary whenever agitation is incorporated into the electrodeposition, and how it will be induced in the bath (e.g. mechanical stirring, electrode movement, ultrasound) [58,59].

2.4.4. Temperature

Temperature significantly impacts electrodeposition processes, as it may influence the structural, morphological, optical, and electrical properties of deposited structures. Precise control over the operating temperature of the electrolyte is therefore essential for consistent performance of electroplating [23]. Temperature directly influences the diffusion and migration of metal ions within the electrolyte [49]; as temperature increases, ion flow at the electrode accelerates due to enhanced ion mobility, which is intrinsically related to lower energy requirements

of the overall process (i.e. higher conductivity results in lower ohmic losses, lower overpotential required for electrodic reactions). The optimal operating temperature generally ranges between 15 and 90 °C depending on the electrodeposition process, with deviations of more than 5 °C potentially affecting finishing quality, deposition rates and other materials properties [24,60]. Temperatures above 100 °C are sometimes used in specific applications to achieve particular structural or compositional requirements that are not achievable at lower temperatures. Nevertheless, electrodeposition at such high temperatures involves several additional challenges: elevated temperatures can accelerate solvent evaporation [61] and induce irreversible phase transformations, thermal softening, or shape changes in metallic substrates [62], potentially resulting in substrate degradation.

Moreover, managing the electrodeposition process with minimal electrolyte heating is crucial for controlling the undesired HER during cathodic electrodeposition [49]. While higher temperatures can promote cathodic efficiency, as demonstrated in the literature [63], they can also escalate HER [64], increasing the risk of hydrogen atoms being trapped in the coating, which may compromise the quality and mechanical performance (e.g. hydrogen embrittlement) [65] of the deposit.

Numerous studies have demonstrated that adjusting the bath temperature can fine-tune the properties of electrodeposited materials, making them suitable for diverse applications. For example, nanostructured CuO thin films electrodeposited from mildly acidic acetic acid baths onto indium-doped tin oxide (ITO)-coated glass for photocatalytic applications transitioned from polycrystalline structures at low temperatures to cubic phases at higher temperatures [66]; as shown in Fig. 5, whereas lower temperatures (20 °C) resulted in dense deposits consisting of fine grains, deposit growth became less uniform as the temperature increased (40 °C), with symmetric-star-like dendrites forming at moderately high temperatures (60 °C) that became rougher with more defects at very high temperatures (80 °C). In this case, CuO electrodeposition at higher temperatures did involve reduced concentration polarisation and yielded materials with lower internal stress, but due to the increase in nucleation rates, the films become rougher with a higher chance to observe potential cracks. This effect of temperature was completely different when a different electrolyte, an alkaline sulfate bath containing tartaric acid, was used to prepare a very similar film (i.e. CuO) in a nearly identical substrate (i.e. ITO-coated glass) [67]. In this case, optimal properties were achieved at 75 °C, with uniform pyramid-shaped grains (200-250 nm) and a band gap of 1.45 eV, providing these films with high refractive index and low band gap suitable for optoelectronic applications. On the other hand, a bath temperature of 40 °C was found to enhance several desirable properties in electrodeposited Cu₂O thin films on fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrates [68]. The films presented increased crystallite size and improved crystalline structure at this temperature, exhibiting well-defined cubic pyramid-shaped grains and superior crystal quality. These films also exhibited a higher optical band gap and better conductivity and photoconductivity, making them particularly suitable for heterojunction solar cell applications.

Controlling the bath temperature is, therefore, an effective tool for customising the electrodeposition process to meet diverse requirements, depending on the application. Temperature influences the surface morphology and structure of electrodeposited ZnO thin films as well; at room temperature, a progressive growth process was observed, transitioning to a more instantaneous one at slightly higher temperatures (°C), which led to a shift from granular to cluster-like structures [69]. In the case of electrodeposited alloys, a good example of the effect of bath temperature is the case of thin NiFeW films, where grain size decreased and crystal orientation changed as the temperature increased from 30 °C to 90 °C [70]; these changes resulted in notable improvements in hardness, magnetisation, and structural properties of the alloy films, making them ideal for nano- and micro-electromechanical systems and memory device applications. Overall, all of these studies demonstrate how bath temperature can be adjusted during electrodeposition to optimise the properties of electrodeposited materials.

Fig. 5. The FESEM images of CuO films prepared under different deposition temperatures under 3 V for 10 min: (a) 20 °C, (b) 40 °C, (c) 60 °C, and (d) 80 °C. Reprinted from Applied Surface Sciences, Vol 317, Yongqian Wang et al., Fabrication of nanostructured CuO films by electrodeposition and their photocatalytic properties, pages 414-421, © 2014, with permission from Elsevier.

2.4.5. Current density

As one might expect from Faraday's Laws of Electrolysis (eq. (1)), the current density (i.e. electric current applied divided by the geometrical or active surface area of the electrode) determines the deposition rate of any electrodeposition process. But this is not the only way current density influences electrodeposition, as the quality and properties of the final deposit can be severely affected by this parameter [23]. Depending on the applied current density, the grain size of electrodeposited materials may not only either increase or decrease [49], but their own crystalline/amorphous nature may change [71]. Generally, higher current densities result in finer-grained deposits due to increased overpotential, which enhances the nucleation process [72–75]; moreover, higher current densities (and the implied greater overpotential) result in a more uniform secondary current distribution, which also leads to a more uniform distribution of electrodeposited metal nuclei [76]. Conversely, lower current densities allow for the growth of larger grains due to the lower nucleation rate [77,78]. Moreover, current density influences the potential appearance of undesired HER and OER at the surface of the cathode or anode in aqueous electrolytes, respectively, which can modify the deposit's surface porosity, overall morphology and even cause hydrogen embrittlement in the case of cathodic electrodeposition.

Pletcher and Walsh provided a comprehensive explanation of deposit growth modes [22], showing that the morphology of metal growth is highly dependent on the current density applied during the process (Fig. 6). At low current densities, metal growth is influenced by dislocation defect patterns, resulting in spiral growth, layered structures, or block formations. When the applied current density is increased, surface diffusion slows down compared to the discharge process, preventing adatoms from reaching their equilibrium positions in the lattice. This phenomenon, along with an increase in the applied overpotential resulting in more frequent nucleation of new growth centres, leads to less ordered lattices and macroscopic features such as ridges or polycrystalline block growth, often valued for enhanced durability. Operating under mixed control conditions typically induces nodular, dendritic growth or the formation of whiskers. However, exceeding the limiting current density (i_L) and fully entering into the mass transport control in the solution presents several challenges. Under mass transport control, electrodeposited materials tend to be powdery in general, adhering poorly to the surface of the electrode. Further exceeding the limiting current density often results in powders with high oxide or hydroxide content due to

Fig. 6. The variation of characteristic growth modes with normalised current density i/i_L . Based on Pletcher and Walsh [22].

intensified HER in aqueous electrolytes, which leads to the local alkalinisation of the electrode/electrolyte interface and favours the formation of oxides or hydroxides.

It is important to note at this point that optimal electrodeposition conditions are not necessarily achieved at the lowest current densities but require experimental determination [79,80]. Even with perfect lattice growth on a substrate with similar lattice dimensions (epitaxial growth), achieving a strongly adhered deposit is not always guaranteed [22]. However, precise control and understanding of the effect of the applied current density enable tailoring microstructural characteristics of electrodeposited materials, optimising them for diverse applications. Adjusting current density can significantly change the properties of thin films, whether the goal is to adjust the surface roughness, control porosity, or adjust grain size. For example, research on the electrodeposition of NiCu alloys on mild steel demonstrated that higher current densities and longer deposition times increased surface roughness and corrosion rates; as current density increased, the deposits transitioned from more compact globular structures to rougher, less compact cauliflower-like morphology, resulting in coating thickness ranging from 2–4 μm at low current densities to 6–8 μm at higher densities [81]. Variations in current density also significantly influenced the texture and corrosion resistance of electrodeposited Sn films electrodeposited on mild steel; whereas coatings deposited at lower current densities presented orientations on the low surface energy (100) plane and exhibited non-uniform stress distribution and poor corrosion resistance, coatings deposited at higher densities presented (110) plane orientations with increased low-angle grain boundaries impacting both uniformity and corrosion resistance [82]. Similarly, studies on bismuth films electrodeposited from high-speed perchlorate electrolytes highlighted the influence of current density on grain size and electronic properties; films deposited at very low current density (0.18 mA/cm^2) presented grain sizes and properties resembling flawless single crystals after annealing, whereas electrodeposition at higher current densities (up to 70.0 mA/cm^2) resulted in more isotropic films with reduced grain sizes, thereby affecting electronic mobility due to increased scattering at grain boundaries [83].

3. Use of electrodeposited materials as catalysts in electrochemical applications

Once the reader has been introduced to electrodeposition processes and the parameters that influence them, it is worth exploring the wide range of electrochemical applications that are benefiting from the ongoing research on electrodeposition methods to synthesise advanced

materials with promising electrocatalytic properties. These range from environmental applications such as electrochemical CO_2 reduction or pollutant removal in water to energy storage applications such as batteries or supercapacitors.

3.1. Electrochemical CO_2 reduction

The electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide is a promising approach towards utilising captures and atmospheric CO_2 to produce valuable renewable fuels and chemical commodities [84–87]. However, the process is also energy-consuming due to the high overpotentials required for several CO_2 reduction reactions [88]. If paired with renewable energy sources like wind or solar, this process could yield valuable chemicals and renewable fuels such as carbon monoxide (CO) [89,90], formic acid (HCOOH) [91,92], methane (CH_4) [93–95], methanol (CH_3OH) [96], ethylene (C_2H_4) [97,98], and ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$) [99].

The vast majority of transition and post-transition metals can be electrodeposited to form electrocatalytic thin films of interest for this application [100]. Cu has gained considerable attention for its capability to produce hydrocarbons and alcohols, achieving reasonably high Faradaic efficiencies for C_{2+} products [101–103]. Metals such as Pb [104], Sn [105], Pd [106] and Zn [107] exhibit high selectivity for the production of formic acid from CO_2 , while Au [108] and Ag [109–111] achieve high Faradaic efficiencies for CO.

The unique capability of electrodeposition processes to allow for precise control over surface morphology, crystal orientation and alloying with other elements facilitates the synthesis of catalysts for the electrochemical reduction of CO_2 with tuned catalytic activity and selectivity [112–115]. For example, studies on Cu foams with hierarchical porosity revealed substantial differences in the distribution and efficiencies of the electrochemical reduction of CO_2 to different products compared to smooth Cu electrodes [103], attributing this effect to factors such as surface roughness and the confinement of reactive species. Similarly, the superior electrocatalytic performance of electrodeposited Bi-based electrocatalysts for the production of formate from CO_2 is linked to their nano-sized structure and surface oxide layer [116].

Fig. 7 illustrates how small changes in both pH of the sulfate bath and applied current density yielded Cu electrocatalysts with completely different structures and surface morphology, resulting in wire, dot, and amorphous structures exhibiting completely different activities and selectivities for different products [113] where wire-structured catalysts achieved notably high efficiencies for C_2 products. Further addition of Ag resulted in CuAg bimetallic catalysts with even greater activity and

Fig. 7. SEM micrographs of Cu films deposited in 0.1 M CuSO_4 and 0.01 M DAT solution at (a) pH 2.5 at -4 mA cm^{-2} , (b) pH 2.5 at -8 mA cm^{-2} , (c) pH 1.5-2 at -4 mA cm^{-2} , (d) pH 1.5-2 at -8 mA cm^{-2} , (e) pH 1 at -4 mA cm^{-2} , and (f) pH 1 at -8 mA cm^{-2} . Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Thao T.H. Hoang et al., Nanoporous Copper Films by Additive-Controlled Electrodeposition: CO_2 Reduction Catalysis, ACS Catalysis 7 (2017) 3313-3321. © 2017 American Chemical Society.

Fig. 8. Faradaic efficiency and current density (normalised to the geometric area) for the electroreduction of CO_2 on the CuAg polycrystalline (black), Cu wire (blue), and CuAg wire (red) samples. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Thao T.H. Hoang et al., Nanoporous Copper-Silver Alloys by Additive-Controlled Electrodeposition for the Selective Electroreduction of CO_2 to Ethylene and Ethanol, Journal of the American Chemical Society 140 (2018) 5791-5797. © 2018 American Chemical Society.

selectivity towards C_{2+} (primarily ethylene but also ethanol) (Fig. 8) [112]. The additive used in these studies, 3,5-diamino-1,2,4-triazole (DAT), significantly influenced crystal formation and growth, resulting in a wire-like morphology. Both Cu and CuAg wire electrocatalysts delivered not just higher current densities for the electrochemical reduction of CO_2 for a certain cathode potential but also achieved significantly higher Faradaic efficiencies compared to CuAg polycrystalline samples. Prior to that, research conducted to develop Ag, AgCu and Cu dendrite structures to act as electrocatalysts for the electrochemical reduction of CO_2 to CO had already demonstrated that by adjusting precursor electrolyte concentrations, it was possible to control catalyst surface structures and compositions [111]; increasing Cu concentration in the electrolyte led to significant morphological changes in AgCu catalysts,

transitioning from round to flower-like shapes with a reduction in the branch size of the dendritic structure. Whereas pure Ag catalysts exhibited the highest Faradaic efficiency for CO production, AgCu dendritic catalysts delivered more than a twofold increase in mass activity.

Recent advancements in electrodeposition techniques have also shown that incorporating multiple metals in a single process can further enhance catalyst performance for the electrochemical reduction of CO_2 . For example, adjusting the proportion of Zn in CuZn catalysts to Cu_4Zn optimised the production of ethanol with such catalysts, resulting in remarkable Faradaic efficiencies and current densities [117]. Additionally, incorporating Hg into CuAg multimetallic thin film catalysts effectively suppressed HER and increased surface concentration of CO binding on the electrode surface, leading to a more efficient electrochemical reduction of CO_2 towards C_{2+} products [118]. However, not all alloy combinations may lead to satisfactory results: although electrodeposition techniques did enable the synthesis of trimetallic NiCuAg 'stack' electrocatalysts that enhanced formic acid production from CO_2 , these were less effective in the conversion of CO_2 to methanol and ethanol than simpler Ni and NiCu electrocatalysts, illustrating that combining multiple metals does not always enhance the performance of electrochemical processes [119].

3.2. Water splitting

In recent years, significant efforts have been made to develop electrocatalysts for water splitting with high activity at a lower cost [120]. The primary challenge in electrolytic water splitting lies in reducing the high overpotentials associated with its two half-cell reactions, which have already been briefly referred to earlier in this review: HER at the cathode and OER at the anode [121]. This process provides a sustainable pathway to produce green hydrogen from renewable electricity, a promising renewable energy source [122,123]. However, the widespread adoption of electrochemical greenhydrogen production is hindered by the high cost of noble metal catalysts such as Pt, Ru, Pd or Ir traditionally used in this application; platinum group metals are recognised for their superior HER performance, while Ir- or Ru-based oxides are considered benchmarks for OER catalysts [124]. To overcome these cost barriers, researchers are exploring cost-effective alternatives using non-precious transition metals such as Ni, Fe and Co, which have demonstrated substantial potential as effective electrocatalysts.

Numerous studies have focused on the synthesis of suitable catalysts for water splitting via electrodeposition, offering advantages over other traditional methods for this application (e.g. chemical and physical vapour deposition, solvo- and hydro-thermal synthesis, ink formulation and spraying); these advantages include versatility, lower cost and precise control of dopant elements, among others [125–127]. For example, nanostructured hematite thin films doped with Zr exhibited enhanced performance for HER compared to undoped films, demonstrating improved photoelectrochemical response with varying levels of Zr doping [126]. Similarly, studies on Pt doping on $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films synthesised by electrodeposition revealed that Pt doping enhanced the photoactivity of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ via improved charge transport properties while diminishing the charge transfer resistance of the film during water oxidation, thus enhancing its electrocatalytic activity [128].

Further advancements have been made using pulse-reversed electrodeposition, which is notable for its ability to tailor the properties of materials such as NiP, optimising their performance in HER and OER [129]. Pulse-reversed electrodeposition involves a dissolution step (i.e. anodic pulse) that significantly influences the electrochemical behaviour of NiP films, enhancing OER activity while decreasing its HER performance; this dual effect was caused by changes in the composition and morphology of the NiP films, which affected the exposure of active sites relevant to either HER or OER. Other electrodeposited structures such as CoFeP on nickel foam have demonstrated promising catalytic activity for both HER and OER in a 1 M KOH electrolyte, exhibiting reasonably efficient kinetics at a relatively low cell voltage potential [130].

Fig. 9. Electrochemical deposition of Cu-based heterojunction ultrathin films. (a) Schematic of deposited Cu monolayer on FTO substrate, (b) cyclic voltammogram obtained in the citric-based electrolyte, derived from e-waste, indicating redox reactions for Cu^{2+} , (c) schematic of deposited $\text{Cu}/\text{Cu}_2\text{O}-\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ bilayer on FTO substrate, (d) cyclic voltammogram obtained in the nitrate-based electrolyte, derived from e-waste, indicating redox reactions for Cu^{2+} and formation of hydroxyl as a result of NO_3^- reduction, and (e) schematic of $\text{Cu}/\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ trilayer on FTO substrate obtained after rapid thermal treatment at $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 min in ambient air. Used with permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry, from Dual functionality of mixed Cu-based two-dimensional (2D) heterostructures derived from electronic waste, Rasoul Khayyam Nekouei et al., *Green Chemistry*, volume 23, pages 5511-5523, 2021; permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc.

Furthermore, novel structures like urchin-like NiFe nanostructured materials exhibited dual activity with low overpotentials for both HER and OER in alkaline media, benefiting from enhanced mass transport and catalytic site availability [131]. Similar results have been obtained with metal and dual-metal chalcogenides and pnictides on different substrates such as CoFeSe on nickel felt [132], CoNiP films on Ti sheets [133], NiCoS on Cu foam [134] and NiP on copper foil [127]. In all these cases, electrodeposition methods were pivotal to the fabrication of high-quality electrocatalytic materials and thin films.

The multi-step electrodeposition approach developed by Nekouei et al. to fabricate Cu-based heterojunction ultrathin films with customizable layers and compositions is perhaps one of the most interesting examples of how electrodeposition can be tailored to produce complex yet effective materials for electrochemical applications [135] (Fig. 9). Initially, a thin Cu monolayer would be deposited onto a fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrate (Fig. 9a) by rapid electrodeposition from a citric-based electrolyte obtained from recycling electronic waste (Fig. 9b). Subsequently, a second layer consisting of Cu_2O and $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ phases was electrodeposited on top (Fig. 9c), this time from a nitric-based electrolyte also obtained from recycling electronic waste (Fig. 9d), again in chronoamperometric conditions. This second layer was rapidly deposited at a very large cathodic overpotential, thus the high content of Cu_2O and $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ due to localised alkalinisation of the electrode/electrolyte interface (see Fig. 6 for further context); in this case, though, the rapid deposition over a very short period of time prevented any potential adhesion issues. The resulting bilayer structure performed quite well as a potential electrode for electrochemical capacitors due to its excellent pseudocapacitance. Moreover, rapid heat treatment at $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in ambient air partially oxidised this bilayer material, which transitioned into a trilayer heterojunction (Fig. 9e) with excellent photoelectrochemical capabilities suitable to become an effective photocathode for HER in photoelectrochemical water splitting. This dual functionality of the Cu-based structures was attributed to their abundant accessible active sites, enhanced electron separation and effective space charge regions across the interfaces.

Overall, the electrodeposited materials discussed in this section show great promise as efficient electrocatalysts for water splitting. However, challenges remain in optimising catalytic performance for both the HER and OER simultaneously. While HER at the cathode is highly developed, OER at the anode presents practical difficulties due to its high overpotential and the risk of H_2-O_2 mixture explosion. To overcome these obstacles, replacing OER with the ammonia oxidation reaction (AOR) offers a promising alternative; this is also an electrochemical reaction where electrodeposition processes can also have a significant impact; in this regard, electrodeposited NiCu-based electrocatalysts have already become a promising option for this process [136,137].

3.3. Degradation of water pollutants

Over the last few decades, water pollution has become a growing global issue, prompting extensive research into practical, sustainable, and cost-effective wastewater treatment strategies. Electrochemical technologies have gained prominence for their operational simplicity, efficiency in pollutant degradation and applicability in diverse environmental conditions [138]. Electrodeposition and ultrasonication have shown promising results in removing heavy metals like copper from wastewater. For instance, Chang et al. [139] demonstrated that this combined approach achieved 95.6% Cu removal and 84% reduction of the Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) from wastewater containing an EDTA-copper complex; the efficiency of copper removal reached 80% after 220 minutes of treatment, with optimal conditions observed at pH 3 and varying potential gradients.

The choice of electrode material significantly influences pollutant degradation efficiency [140]. Lead dioxide (PbO_2) films have attracted attention due to their affordability, high electrical conductivity, elevated overpotential for OER and excellent stability under controlled conditions. These films offer diverse phase structures and morphologies, which can be achieved through both doped and undoped materials [141]. For example, Pillai et al. [142] investigated the electrochemical degradation of organic pollutants using a PbO_2 electrode prepared via potentiostatic electrodeposition on a mild steel plate substrate, find-

ing that operational parameters such as applied current, initial dye concentration and electrolyte composition significantly influenced reaction kinetics, current efficiency, and energy consumption during the degradation of methyl orange. The incorporation of ultrasound to the electrodeposition of PbO_2 electrocatalytic films further enhances their properties and lifespan [143], contributing to the complete removal of chlorinated organic compounds in drinking water by sonoelectrochemical methods [144–146]. Similarly, mixing PbO_2 with other transition metal oxides SnO_2 or doping it with other metals such as La resulted in effective electrocatalysts for the electrochemical degradation of compounds such as the antibiotic enrofloxacin [147]. The presence of TiO_2 nanoparticles can also facilitate the electrocrystallisation of PbO_2 , resulting in enhanced electrode performance for water treatment via $\cdot\text{OH}$ radical generation from water discharge [148].

Electrodeposited manganese oxide materials have also been studied and developed for electrochemical water remediation. Electrodeposited Mn_yO_x films have been evaluated as visible-light-driven photocatalysts for removing the antibiotic tetracycline [149], showing that both *pH* of the bath and post-electrodeposition annealing were key to deliver optimised electrocatalysts achieving 92.4% mineralisation efficiency in optimal conditions under LED illumination; $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals were again identified as the primary active species for the degradation of the antibiotic. Electrodeposited thin films of $\text{Mn}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ also exhibited robust photoelectrochemical properties for the degradation of organic pollutants in water, achieving 95% degradation of Rhodamine B and 79% COD reduction within 25 minutes of operation due to their good n-type conduction and excellent stability [150].

3.4. Energy storage

Electrochemical energy systems are promising alternatives for energy supply and storage due to their direct energy conversion without intermediate steps, minimal moving parts, high conversion efficiency, and potential for miniaturisation and portability [151]. These systems are typically classified into three main categories: batteries, fuel cells, and supercapacitors, each with distinct advantages and limitations. Often, the requirements for energy storage, such as response time, power capability, and energy density, exceed the performance limits of current energy technology and even the theoretical limits of a specific technology [152]. Consequently, there is a significant demand for hybrid energy solutions that can optimise cost, efficiency, reliability, and lifespan while meeting specific performance needs.

Extensive efforts have been dedicated to the development and improvement of cleaner and more efficient storage solutions to optimise their performance and expand their applicability [153–155]. Conventional and nanostructured materials used in electrochemical energy conversion and storage technologies can be synthesised through various methods, including chemical vapour deposition [156], electrodeposition [157], spray pyrolysis [158], galvanic replacement reactions [159], hydrothermal synthesis [160], electrospinning [161] and by using molten salts [162]. Among these, electrodeposition processes hold particular importance for the fabrication of electrochemical energy devices.

3.4.1. Batteries

A battery is an energy storage device that converts chemical energy into electrical energy. There are two main types of batteries: primary and secondary. The key difference between them is that secondary batteries can be recharged and then reused again. Besides being the main technology in use for small and portable devices, secondary (rechargeable) battery systems are emerging as a promising energy storage technology for grid-scale applications. They offer high energy conversion efficiency and high energy and power density while maintaining relatively straightforward maintenance requirements [163].

In general, the requirements for secondary batteries must consider battery power and energy densities, potential, capacity, response time,

Fig. 10. Schematic of the fabrication of Au nanoparticles deposited on a Ni nanowire substrate using an electrodeposition method. Reprinted from S. T. Kim et al., Optimization of carbon- and binder-free Au nanoparticle-coated Ni nanowire electrodes for Lithium-Oxygen Batteries, *Advanced Energy Materials* 5 (2015) 1401030. With permission from John Wiley and Sons. © 2014 WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim.

charge-discharge rates, safety, and economic efficiency to ensure efficient performance [164]. However, no secondary battery fully satisfies all these criteria, as the standards for high-performance effectiveness vary according to the type of secondary battery. Based on their electrode components, common types of rechargeable batteries include lead-acid, lithium-ion, nickel-metal hydride, and nickel-cadmium technologies [165]. Among these, lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are the most promising and widely used secondary battery type [166–168].

Electrodeposition is a widely used technique for fabricating nearly all components of LIBs, including the cathode, anode, current collector, and electrolyte. Unlike traditional methods, electrodeposition allows for the rapid and flexible deposition of thin films; this flexibility not only optimises battery performance but also allows for the development of novel battery designs that would be more challenging to materialise with other technologies [169]. For example, a recent study demonstrated the innovative fabrication of $\text{CuSn}/\text{nano-SiO}_2$ composite anode materials for LIBs using electrodeposition combined with precise thermal treatment [170], resulting in a more uniform and compact composite electrode structure after adjusting the current density applied during the fabrication process. This change contributed to enhancing the electrochemical performance, providing the electrode with high capacity while maintaining structural stability after several charge/discharge cycles. Another interesting development achieved by electrodeposition is the fabrication of efficient Au/Ni electrodes for $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries [171], where Ni nanowires were grown on an aluminium oxide membrane template via electrodeposition (Fig. 10). The researchers were also able to electrodeposit Au nanoparticles, each less than 30 nm in size, on the Ni nanowires, minimising the amount of Au used while maximising the number of active sites. The optimised Au/Ni electrode exhibited a remarkable capacity of $921 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}_{\text{Au}}$ at a current density of 300 mA per g of deposited Au and maintained exceptional cycle stability over 200 charge/discharge cycles. Redox-flow batteries have also benefited from the unique advantages of electrodeposition processes to fabricate electrode materials, as illustrated by the work conducted on the electrodeposition of Pt on porous titanium electrodes for Ce-based flow batteries [172–174].

The versatility of electrodeposition techniques has also been used by many research groups to create porous architectures to enhance the performance of battery electrodes. For example, electrodeposited porous cobalt oxide (Co_3O_4) array films used as anodes for LIBs exhibited notable cycling performance and discharge capacities due to their high porosity and large surface area, providing efficient contact between electrolyte and the oxide surface while minimising the diffusion length for Li^+ [175]. Similarly, precise tuning of deposition parameters such as potential, precursor ratios, and substrate roughness enabled the electrode-

position of interconnected nanoporous ZnSb architectures on Cu foils (e.g. nanoflakes, nanowires, nanoparticles) also used as negative electrodes in LIBs (i.e. anode during discharge and cathode during charging [176]). The interconnected ZnSb nanoflakes exhibited superior electrochemical performance compared to the same material in nanoparticle or nanowire form, achieving a discharge capacity of 500 mAh g⁻¹ with a Coulombic efficiency of 98% after 70 cycles at a current density of 100 mA g⁻¹. This improvement in performance could again be attributed to their open porous structure consisting of small grains, which provides a large surface area that facilitates Li⁺ diffusion while buffering volume changes during the lithium intercalation process.

It is important to note that electrodeposition processes are not meant to replace other battery manufacturing methods but to complement and enhance them [169]. An example is the development of a LIB using fibre-type Li-rich positive electrode and carbon negative electrode materials [177], where the researchers applied an electrodeposition-assisted approach to synthesise the positive electrode material onto carbon fibre tow. Initially, the precursor was formed via electrodeposition, followed by the production of the active material through hydrothermal treatment; the resulting cell demonstrated rapid activation, favourable Coulombic efficiency, and high-rate performance, highlighting the structural advantages of fibre-type electrodes for electrical conduction and ion diffusion. A further example is the combination of sol-gel and anodic electrodeposition techniques to synthesise mica-like V₂O₅ nanostructured thin films [178]. These electrodes displayed good cyclic performance, with a storage capacity of 596 mAh g⁻¹ at the current density of 1080 mA g⁻¹ and excellent cyclic stability and reversibility; moreover, the electrodes kept their morphology, lost only 0.48% of their capacity per cycle, and maintained their structural integrity after 50 charge/discharge cycles.

These advancements highlight the versatility and power of electrodeposition in advancing battery technology. By offering precise control over material structure and composition, electrodeposition facilitates the creation of high-performance electrodes that significantly enhance battery efficiency and durability.

3.4.2. Supercapacitors

A supercapacitor is a high-capacity energy storage device characterised by its high power density, extended cycle life, and rapid charging and discharging efficiency [179,180]. These advantages make supercapacitors valuable for various applications, including portable electronics, transportation, power backup systems, biomedical devices, military applications, and aerospace technology [181]. The design of electrode materials is crucial for achieving the high energy and power densities required for supercapacitors [182]. Research has predominantly focused on three main categories of active electrode materials: carbon-based materials, conductive polymers, and transition metal oxides [183–187]. Among these, various electrodeposited transition metal oxides, such as Fe₂O₃ [188], Mn₃O₄ [189], MoO₃ [190], and Bi₂O₃ [191], have demonstrated excellent capacitance, making them promising candidates for supercapacitor applications.

Many of these studies have focused on the properties of electrodeposited manganese oxide films and their use in supercapacitors. Electrodeposited MnO₂ thin films on activated carbon paper exhibited excellent capacitance performance (485.4 F g⁻¹ at 2 A g⁻¹) due to its enlarged specific surface area and improved electronic conductivity [192]; moreover, its accessibility of electrolytic ions, which resulted in the full utilisation of the MnO₂ active material, provided it with a greater rate capability compared to other active electrode materials. Electrodeposition techniques using porous alumina templates also delivered MnO₂ nanotubes and nanowires, where increasing deposition time resulted in a transition from tubular to wire-like morphology via [182]. In this case, the capacitive behaviour of the MnO₂ nanotube array electrode was superior to that of the nanowire array electrode: such superiority could be attributed to the unique nanotubular design that offers fast ion and electron transport; the MnO₂ nanotube array electrode also exhib-

ited good enough rate capability and cycling stability suitable for supercapacitor applications. Mn₃O₄ thin films were also electrodeposited under potentiodynamic conditions from a KMnO₄ solution to develop cost-effective, high-performance electrodes for flexible supercapacitors with long cyclic life [193]. After electrodeposition, the films were annealed at different temperatures (i.e. 150, 200 and 250 °C), resulting in progressive material phase modification from Mn₃O₄ to α -MnO₂ that influenced their pseudo-capacitance, depending on the electrolyte being used. More recently, electrodeposition techniques were capable of maximising the benefits of highly porous Pt scaffolds by delivering RuO₂ that, along with the Pt scaffold, achieved record capacitance and energy storage values, illustrating the scalability and commercial promise of the electrodeposition of catalysts over advanced supports for a wide range of materials and devices beyond supercapacitors, including batteries, fuel cells and sensors [194].

3.4.3. Fuel cells

Fuel cells are electrochemical energy conversion devices that continuously receive fuels such as hydrogen, natural gas or methanol, along with an oxidant such as oxygen, air or hydrogen peroxide, and convert that chemical energy into electricity [195]. Although a fuel cell is comparable to a traditional battery, it differs significantly in the way they operate: a battery stops producing electrical energy once its chemical reactants are consumed; in contrast, a fuel cell is an energy conversion device that, as long as it continues to receive both fuel and oxidant, will generate electricity (and heat) [196].

To facilitate this conversion process, fuel cells utilise complex electrode structures that ensure a stable interface between the reactant gas and the electrolyte, catalyse electrode reactions and conduct electrons [195]. Electrodeposition is particularly effective for preparing highly active thin films for fuel cell applications due to its flexibility in regulating parameters such as morphology, crystallographic orientation, and electrode thickness. For example, accurate control of the applied current density during the electrodeposition of Pt electrocatalysts on carbon cathodes for polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) enabled the fabrication of three-dimensional ultra-fine Pt nanoflowers that exhibited enhanced performance in the reduction of oxygen gas due to their unique morphology characterised by anisotropic growth and optimised particle distribution (Fig. 11) [197]. Similarly, careful selection of electrolyte composition and control of both deposition potential and process duration enabled the production of catalysts with excellent methanol oxidation activity and tolerance towards CO poisoning [198].

In the case of metal oxides, the adoption of electrodeposition techniques facilitated the creation of fibrous MnO₂ electrodes on carbon fibres that exhibited superior electrochemical properties due to excellent connectivity and high charge-transfer rates [199]; the electrodeposition process adopted for their fabrication allowed for more precise control over the thickness of the catalysts, resulting in a high specific surface area and lower overpotential requirements for the oxygen reduction reaction and enhancing the overall efficiency of the fuel cell.

3.5. Sensors

Sensors are electronic devices with an active sensing material coupled with a signal transducer [200]. These components transmit signals directly from a selective compound or a change in a reaction without amplification. Sensors generate electrical, thermal, or optical output signals, which can be converted into digital signals for further processing. The ability to control the nucleation and growth rate of metal nanoparticles during electrodeposition makes this approach particularly attractive for synthesising metallic nanostructures for sensor applications [201].

There are many examples in the literature where electrodeposition processes have been used to develop advanced sensor materials. A good example is the low-cost, easy-to-fabricate amperometric sensor for (NO₃⁻) detection in water consisting of a silver electrode modified with electrodeposited copper nanoclusters (Fig. 12) with high catalytic

Fig. 11. FE-SEM images of Pt electrocatalysts electrodeposited on carbon electrode for 15 min at different current densities: (a) 1.6, (b) 3.2, (c) 8, (d) 16, (e) 24 and (f) 32 mA cm⁻². Reprinted from Journal of Colloid and Interface Science, Vol 572, P. Dhanasekaran et al. Electrochemical deposition of three-dimensional platinum nanoflowers for high-performance polymer electrolyte fuel cells, pages 198–206, © 2020, with permission from Elsevier.

Fig. 12. Schematic illustration of the fabrication process and the detection mechanism of the proposed nitrate (NO_3^-) sensor: (A) Screen-printed silver (Ag) WE (B) modified with electrodeposited copper (Cu), leading to (C) NO_3^- reduction. (D) Micrograph of the cost-effective, flexible, screen-printed electrochemical NO_3^- sensor. Reprinted from A. S. Inam et al., Flexible screen-printed electrochemical sensors functionalised with electrodeposited copper for nitrate detection in water, ACS Omega 6 (2021) 33523–33532. © 2021 A. S. Inam, M. A. Costa Angeli, B. Shkodra, A. Douaki, E. Avancini, L. Magagnin, L. Petti and P. Lugli. CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0.

activity and a sensitivity of 19.578 $\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}$, a low detection limit of 0.207 nM, and a good dynamic linear concentration range from 0.05 to 5 mM, which exhibited negligible interference from common analytes and effectively detected nitrate in real water samples [202]. Similarly, a cost-effective method for detecting oxalic acid (OA) was developed using one-step co-electrodeposition to create a porous silicon matrix with platinum nanoparticles that exhibited better reproducibility, stability, and selectivity than existing alternatives, showing great potential for practical applications [203].

The electrodeposition of metal oxides has also been widely explored to develop sensible electrochemical sensors. CuBi_2O_4 thin films electrodeposited on FTO glass were used as an electrochemical sensor for uric acid and hydrogen peroxide, achieving high sensitivities of up to 206.7 and 280.6 $\mu\text{A mM}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ for each molecule, respectively, indicating their suitability for sensing applications [204]. ZnO was also

electrodeposited on GaN to create flower-like structures that exhibited exceptional ethanol sensing performance at room temperature; these electrodes featured high sensitivity, rapid response and excellent selectivity, where the heterojunction formed at the GaN interface significantly improved the sensing performance compared to single ZnO sensing material [205], demonstrating that both morphology and structure of electrodeposited materials are critical for gas sensor performance.

Electrodeposited nanostructured materials have also received wide attention from the research community. For example, Ag nanoparticles electrodeposited on a glassy carbon electrode modified with natural nanostructured attapulgite were also used to develop a novel sensor for hydrogen peroxide [206], where both attapulgite content and electrodeposition parameters were critical to optimise the performance of the device. Vertically aligned WO_3 nanoflakes were also produced via electrodeposition for various sensor applications [207] due to the excellent electrochromic performance, significant optical modulation, faster response times, higher colouration efficiency and excellent cyclic stability of the material. More recently, hexagonal plate-like Zn nanostructures were electrodeposited on anodised TiO_2 nanotube arrays in potentiostatic conditions to make implantable electrochemical sensors [208]. The crystallinity and morphology of the TiO_2 substrates played crucial roles in promoting well-shaped zinc deposits while increasing the deposition time led to denser and more vertically oriented Zn layers. Overall, by optimising the electrodeposition process parameters, researchers have developed sensors with enhanced sensitivity, stability, and selectivity, opening the way for practical and efficient detection technologies.

4. Challenges and future opportunities

Although electrodeposition processes are well established in both Industry and Academia, many researchers and engineers outside of the Surface Finishing industry experience a lack of understanding of the influence of process parameters such as those discussed earlier and the most convenient approach towards their optimisation. The general lack of understanding of their role and the importance of their optimisation is not only reflected in other reviews on the topic published before this paper but especially in many recent studies focused on electrodeposited electrocatalysts where the effect and optimisation of these parameters is generally overlooked [209–213]. Addressing this unawareness would unlock new opportunities to significantly enhance the performance of electrodeposited catalysts while optimising their manufacturing process by just finding the right process parameters [214].

Looking ahead, pulse electrodeposition constitutes a promising option for further tuning catalyst properties. Although we did introduce pulse electrodeposition earlier, it still remains relatively unexplored as a method for catalyst fabrication due to the advanced expertise in electroplating and surface finishing it requires. Further implementation of pulse electrodeposition methods may lead to enhanced electrocatalyst distribution and electrocatalyst/support interaction, as well as porosity, ductility, electrical conductivity and thickness distribution of the electrodeposited electrocatalytic materials [215]; moreover, this approach may also enable tuning the composition along the material thickness to further enhance its mechanical properties (i.e. adhesion to support) and electrocatalytic performance (e.g. formation of heterostructures using different metals deposited under different pulse conditions) [216]. Thinking outside the box by adopting process design strategies that may initially be at odds by more ‘classical’ and conservative electrodeposition approaches may also present some interesting options for research. For example, although electrodeposition under heavy HER may lead to poorly adhered powders with high oxide and hydroxide content (Fig. 6) [22], it is possible to minimise this issue to produce heterojunction structures with metals and metal oxides (Fig. 9) [135] or porous catalyst structures with larger electroactive surface areas [217,218]. These strategies, combined with a deeper understanding of process parameters, offer exciting opportunities for advancing the application of electrodeposition in electrocatalysis.

5. Conclusions

This review comprehensively explores the electrodeposition processes, highlighting their versatility, cost-effectiveness and efficiency towards fabricating advanced nano- and micro-structured materials and thin films for various electrochemical applications. The fundamental principles of electrodeposition, such as its mechanisms, methods (i.e. potentiostatic, galvanostatic and pulse techniques), and the effects of key process parameters (i.e. electrolyte, *pH*, temperature and current density) have been thoroughly discussed, illustrating how each of these factors, combined or on their own, plays a critical role in defining the structural and functional properties of electrodeposited electrode materials.

The review also highlights the crucial role of electrodeposited materials in several electrochemical applications, ranging from electrocatalysts for the electrochemical reduction of CO₂ or water splitting to their use in energy storage devices such as batteries and supercapacitors. The ability of electrodeposition processes to enable fine control over surface texture and distribution, crystallographic orientation and (when relevant) alloy composition is critical to enhance the activity, selectivity, and durability of electrocatalysts. Moreover, the unique flexibility of electrodeposition processes to a wide range of substrates and complex surface geometries illustrate their potential for large-scale industrial applications aimed at addressing the pressing challenges of renewable energy production and environmental sustainability. The diversity of electrodeposited materials and the ability to fine-tune their properties open up a wide range of applications, particularly in environmental and sensing applications. Advanced electrodeposited electrocatalysts for the removal of water pollutants and high-sensitivity sensors for chemical detection showcase the practical benefits of this technique. On the other hand, the review also identifies a certain unawareness within the research community regarding the role of process parameters and their optimisation, which could unlock new opportunities to enhance the performance of electrodeposited electrocatalysts. Moreover, the potential of pulse electrodeposition and the development of innovative process strategies, such as electrodeposition under heavy HER conditions, has been discussed as potential options for future research.

In conclusion, electrodeposition remains an extremely important manufacturing method in modern material science and electrochemical engineering. Its flexibility and efficiency make it an essential tool in the development of innovative solutions to global challenges, from renewable energy production to environmental sustainability. Future research should continue to explore novel electrodeposition methods, materials and process optimisation to further expand the applicability and impact of this technology across various sectors.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mayra S. Tovar-Oliva: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ignacio Tudela:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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